

MODELLING PHOTOGRAMMETRIC DATASETS IN ORDER TO ENHANCE URBAN PLANNING

Iuliana M. PÂRVU¹ Iuliana A. CUIBAC PICU¹
Adrian PÂRVU¹ Marinela CRISTACHE²

Abstract: *This paper explores the application of photogrammetric datasets to enhance urban planning through the development of detailed 3D city models. Using high-precision photogrammetric data, a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) was derived from dense image matching point cloud, in order to accurately extract the ground of the urban landscape. A Digital Surface Model (DSM) was also generated, capturing all features, including buildings and vegetation. The subtraction of the DTM from the DSM produces a normalized Digital Surface Model (nDSM), isolating the height of above ground features such as buildings. The nDSM is important to extract building heights. Using building footprints and the extracted height values, a LoD2 building model was developed. These models provide accurate representations of buildings, including roof shapes and heights, crucial for urban planning tasks such as infrastructure design and environmental analysis. This approach will try to demonstrate how integrating photogrammetry with advanced modelling techniques can significantly improve the accuracy and utility of urban planning tools.*

Keywords: *DSM, DTM, 3D building models, photogrammetry.*

1. Introduction

Urban planning has become increasingly reliant on advanced technologies to manage the complexities of modern cities. In particular, the integration of photogrammetry — the science of transforming 2D images into 3D models — has proven to be a powerful tool for collecting spatial data essential for urban development [24]. Photogrammetric datasets, generated using high-resolution

aerial imagery or terrestrial data offer an efficient means of mapping urban environments with high precision. However, the raw data from photogrammetric surveys often require advanced modelling techniques to be fully utilized in practical urban planning scenarios. The application of modelling techniques to photogrammetric datasets enhances the ability to accurately represent three-dimensional structures of urban landscapes. Recent advances in

¹ National Center of Cartography, Expozitiei Blv. 1A, Bucharest, Romania;

² S.C. Primul Meridian S.R.L., Vintila Voda street 50, Slatina, Romania;

Correspondence: Iuliana Maria Pârvu; email: iuliana.parvu@cartografie.ro .

computational algorithms, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence, have further improved the processing and analysis of these datasets, providing planners with more detailed and actionable insights. This is critical in areas such as infrastructure planning and environmental impact assessments, where the ability to predict and visualize changes to urban spaces is vital for effective decision-making [16]. By integrating time-series data from photogrammetric surveys, urban planners can track long-term trends and assess the effectiveness of planning strategies. For instance, the use of 3D city models in combination with geographic information systems (GIS) allows planners to simulate various scenarios, optimize land use, and enhance the design of urban spaces [25]. Despite the significant potential, challenges remain regarding the modelling of photogrammetric datasets effectively. Issues such as data noise, the need for high computational power, and the integration of heterogeneous data sources must also be addressed. Furthermore, the complexity of modelling urban environments accurately requires interdisciplinary collaboration between fields such as geospatial science, architecture, and urban planning. This article explores the current methodologies for modelling photogrammetric datasets and examines their applications in urban planning, with a focus on the potential for enhancing urban sustainability, mobility, and resilience when facing rapid urbanization [22].

2. 3D Building Models and Urban Planning

The modern city is often regarded as a connecting point between administrative-governmental functions with its citizens in

domains such as economy, transportation, communication, technology, and services. Consequently, there is an increasing need for carefully planning the development of urban areas, which extends beyond the existing city boundaries to encompass the continuous growth and development of adjacent areas [18]. Another significant challenge for modern cities is climate change, which has long posed threats to urban environments. Urban centres have substantial energy demands for spatial conditioning and population mobility [13], contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. Government policies, administrative initiatives, and external factors, such as climate change and urban planning, directly influence the development of modern cities. Climate change exerts significant pressure on urban areas, requiring city leaders to address its impacts while ensuring that climate resilience becomes a cornerstone of municipal governance.

This was the starting point for the project Climate Resilient Development Pathways in Metropolitan Regions of Europe – CARMINE [9]. The project's goal is to assist metropolitan communities in Europe in becoming more resilient to climate change through the co-production of knowledge-based tools, strategies, and plans for enhanced adaptation and mitigation actions, aligned with the EU Mission Charter on Climate Adaptation by 2030. To achieve this objective, focusing on the 2030–2035 timeframe and with longer-term perspectives extending to 2050, CARMINE proposes an interdisciplinary approach that aims to:

- Co-create and co-develop decision-support services and guidelines to enhance resilience and adaptive capacity, including early warning

systems and disaster risk management frameworks;

- Cooperate closely with local and regional communities (stakeholders and users), policymakers, and decision-makers (local authorities) to co-develop cross-sectoral frameworks for adaptation and mitigation actions;
- Deliver science-based research and innovation solutions for multi-level climate governance, supporting local adaptation assessments and planning efforts.

CARMINE carries out its approach in eight Case Study Areas (CSA): Prague (CZ), Leipzig (DE), Funen-Odense (DK), Athens (GR), Barcelona (ES), Bologna (IT), Brasov (RO), and Birmingham (UK) [9]. In every CSA, a Living Lab will be developed in order to analyse the climate risks and socio-economic vulnerabilities. The final goal is to co-design decision-support tools and propose climate-resilient development pathways through the use of Digital Twins.

3D city models consist of 3D models of buildings, vegetation, street elements, urban infrastructure (e.g. hydrographic constructions, high voltage lines), and urban objects (e.g. traffic signs, monuments, statues and fountains). High resolution Digital Surface Models (*DSMs*) include all these elements, but do not distinguish between individual objects.

Therefore, generating 3D models from point cloud datasets is the best option, as it preserves accuracy and facilitates analysis at an individual level. There are three methods of generating 3D building models: model-based, data-based, and hybrid. For the model-based generation of 3D building models, a building is considered to be made up of simple primitives, stored in a library of predefined models. In the case of complex buildings, the reconstruction approach is to decompose the building into multiple shapes and to match the models to these shapes. For the data-based generation of 3D building models, no assumptions are made about the shape of the buildings. These methods use point cloud segmentation, followed by individual segment assembly and model reconstruction. The methods used for segmentation include algorithms such as region growing, RANSAC [5].

The geometric and semantic detailing of a 3D model is known as the level of detail (*LoD*). Standardization defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (*OGC*) is known as the CityGML standard [19]. In the CityGML version 2.0 five standard classes with different *LoDs* are defined (Figure 1). Higher levels have a superior degree of detail, are more precise, and have a structure of greater complexity.

Fig. 1. *LoDs* in CityGML 2.0 [1]

By combining 3D modelling with meteorological data in order to create a digital twin (*DT*) of the area, urban planners can foster sustainable development, enhance resilience, and improve the quality of life for urban residents. Digital twins were initially developed in manufacturing, representing high-fidelity digital plans of products to be made [12]. The defining feature of a *DT* is that the entire planning process occurs digitally, without further adjustments once the *DT* model is finalized and production begins. In construction, *DTs* align closely with Building Information Modelling (*BIM*), which consists of high-fidelity three-dimensional construction plans. These models may require adjustments for landscape integration, such as in the case of single form-work concrete bridges [7]. For urban environments, *DTs* aim to replicate essential physical and functional properties, including buildings, infrastructure, vegetation, terrain, and other elements. They also enable the integration of information from various processes. Creating *DTs* for urban environments involves 3D models derived from point clouds and/or images, which are considered data derivatives [15].

Based on the integration of photogrammetric data with advanced modelling techniques, a 3D model of the buildings is generated that could be used by decision-makers for various analyses and applications [2], also taking into account the city's climate data, thus improving the urban planning of the area. One application is the urban microclimate analysis, where detailed 3D building models enhanced with meteorological data are used to simulate airflow, temperature distribution, and solar radiation. This

enables planners to mitigate urban heat island effects and optimize building orientation and material selection for better thermal performance [20]. Another key application is disaster risk management. 3D models integrated with real-time weather data allow for accurate simulations of flood risks and wind impacts in urban areas, facilitating the design of adaptive infrastructure and early warning systems [14]. The integration also supports green infrastructure planning. 3D models enriched with meteorological insights help identify optimal locations for parks, green roofs, and urban forests, improving air quality and reducing surface runoff during heavy rain events [6].

3. Case Study

3.1. Research area

We aim to demonstrate how the integration of photogrammetry with advanced modelling techniques can significantly improve the accuracy and utility of urban planning tools. The study area consists of 2 sq. km in the town Măgurele, in Ilfov County (Figure 2).

3.2. National Project for High Resolution Image Acquisition in Romania

The data used for the case study are derived from the ongoing national project for high resolution image acquisition in Romania [4]. The project's primary activities include acquiring high-resolution aerial imagery, conducting bundle block adjustment and dense image matching, and generating digital surface models (*DSMs*) and true orthophotos. Figure 3 shows the project areas at city level. The aerial data acquisition is done using

advanced photogrammetric sensors. The images are composed of four spectral bands (red, green, blue, and near-infrared) and the spatial resolution is of 4, 9 or 15 cm, depending on the city type.

Fig. 2. Study area

Fig. 3. True orthophoto generation in Romania

The main outputs of the project are delivered in the national Romanian reference system (Krasovski ellipsoid 1940, Stereographic projection 1970, and Black Sea normal altitude system 1975). The main outputs of the project are photogrammetric images, photogrammetric-derived point clouds via Structure-from-Motion (*SfM*), DSMs and true orthophotos. All products are

3.3. Data Acquisition

The aerial flight was carried out in April 2022, using an oblique ULTRACAM Osprey

4.1 camera produced by Vexcel. The main technical specifications of the photogrammetric flight are displayed in Table 1.

Dataset parameters

Table 1

CAMERA PARAMETERS	Digital camera	UltraCam Osprey 4.1
	Focal length of the nadir sensor	79.6 mm
	Image Format (long track and cross track)	52.700 mm 77.245 mm
	Pixel size	3.760 μm x 3.760 μm
	Coordinates of the principal point	0.000 mm 0.000 mm
FLIGHT SPECS	Spatial image resolution	15 - 16.5 cm
	Spectral resolution	4 bands (R,G,B,NIR)
	Frontal overlap	78% - 82%
	Side overlap	58% - 62%
	Average flight height	3,365 m
	Flight days	24.04.2022 26.04.2022
	Number of images	2892
	Number of flight lines	41
	Block surface	1,518 sq. km
	Flight direction	East-West
	Number of GCPs	58 points
	Number of CHKs	57 points

The flight was performed in good meteorological conditions and the dataset obtained (raw images, GNSS and IMU measurements) went through a rigorous photogrammetric workflow, consisting of:

1. *Image Processing*: includes enhancing the geometric and radiometric image quality;
2. *Tie points extraction*: represents extracting the corresponding points in two or more overlapping images. Tie point identification can be done by brute force, which involves comparing each descriptor of image A with each descriptor of image B. This approach is simple, but quite inefficient. Examples

of alternative strategies are: FLANN [17, 23], which uses a quick search structure, and MatchMe [21], which uses similarity measurements between descriptors;

3. *Bundle adjustment*: the 3D coordinates of the points and the exterior orientation parameters are determined based on the internal orientation parameters, the coordinates and the rotation angles measured for each projection centre and the previously identified tie points, and the GCPs coordinates. Both tie point extraction and bundle adjustment can be done with specialized software, such as Inpho

Match-AT (Trimble) or UltraMap (Vexcel);

4. Dense image matching: To obtain a dense point cloud, a corresponding point is needed for all the pixels in the image. SGM (semi-global matching) is a computer vision algorithm for the estimation of a dense disparity map from a rectified stereo image pair [8]. The method is used nowadays, also in improved versions.

The quality assessment of the aerial triangulation was performed using the check points (*CHKs*) that were precisely determined in the field using static GNSS observations and geometric levelling measurements. GNSS data were acquired with a minimum observation time of two hours per point and a sampling interval of 10 seconds. A total of 11 simultaneous measurements were performed to ensure the establishment of baseline vectors between the determined points. The GNSS measurements were made using Spectra

Precision SP80 (240-channel) and E-Survey E300 PRO (800-channel) receivers, which support signals from GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, and BeiDou with subsequent data processing carried out using Spectra Survey Office software to guarantee accurate adjustments and coordinate transformations. The normal height of the GCPs and CHKs were determined through precise geometric levelling, and referenced to the National Levelling Network. For this purpose, digital levels, FOCUS DL-15, with an accuracy of 1.5 mm per double kilometre were used. The planimetric Root Mean Square Error ($RMSE_{XY}$ - Equations (1) to (3)) obtained was 9.14 cm and the altimetric RMSE ($RMSE_H$ - Equation (4)) was 17.61 cm, based on the 57 CHK. The densified photogrammetric-derived point cloud is comprised of 128 million points, with a density of approximately 60 points/sq m (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. *Input datasets: photogrammetric point cloud and building footprints*

$$RMSE_X = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - X_i^{ref})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE_Y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - Y_i^{ref})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$RMSE_{XY} = \sqrt{RMSE_X^2 + RMSE_Y^2} \quad (3)$$

$$RMSE_H = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (H_i - H_i^{ref})^2} \quad (4)$$

where:

X_i, Y_i, H_i represent the measured coordinates in stereomodels for the CHKs [m];

$X_i^{ref}, Y_i^{ref}, H_i^{ref}$ – the field coordinates of the CHKs [m];

n – the number of CHKs.

The national topographic database TopRo5 (at a scale of 1:5.000) was used to extract the building footprints [10]. All geospatial features were digitized using the INSPIRE Directive based on the infrastructures for spatial information established and operated by the Member States of the European Union [11].

3.4. Proposed Workflow

The CityEngine software, developed by Esri, uses a 3D generation procedure based on a series of rule files, written in a programming language called Computer Generated Architecture (CGA). These rules underlie the extrusion of polygons and the generation of 3D building models (Figure 5). Textures for buildings can also be added to the rules file.

Fig. 4. 3D building models using CityEngine

This approach requires information about the building footprints and the height of each individual building. These heights can be derived from data stored by public entities or from processed photogrammetric datasets and were introduced as an attribute.

In our approach, heights were extracted from the normalized Digital Surface Model (*nDSM*) and were assigned to the building footprints as attributes. To model the buildings in a 3D environment, the workflow in Figure 6 was conducted.

Fig. 6. Proposed workflow for 3D building modelling

The point cloud classification was performed in TerraScan using routines defined in a macro. The study area was analyzed and parameters used in the classification process, like building surface area, building heights, and maximum height for vegetation, were extracted from the data and included in the macro. Digital models were generated in Global Mapper using the *TIN* interpolation method, in raster format at a spatial resolution of 20 cm, as follows: digital terrain model (*DTM* - from ground points), digital surface model (*DSM* - from ground and non-ground points), and normalized digital surface model (*nDSM* - based on the arithmetic difference between *DSM* and *DTM* - Figure

7).

In order to assign the height values to the building footprints, geoprocessing tools from ArcGIS were used. The approach was based on the research performed by Bină [3]:

- Using the "Feature to Points" tool, the centroid points of the buildings were generated;
- Using "Extract Values to Points" tool, the pixel height value corresponding to the centroid point was extracted from the *nDSM*;
- By applying a spatial join between the centroid points and the footprints, the building height was transferred to the polygons.

Fig. 7. Normalized digital surface model

The software used for 3D building models, CityEngine, uses a 3D generation procedure based on a series of CGA rule files. The principle is based on polygon extrusion, followed by generation of 3D

building models.

For the quality assessment, the root mean square error of the building heights was computed (Equation (5)).

$$RMSE_H = \sqrt{\frac{(H_{ground_truth} - H_{3D_model})^2}{n}} \quad (5)$$

4. Results

The study area consists of 2 sq km in the town Măgurele, in Ilfov County (as shown previously). After performing the steps described above, the heights of the buildings were extracted from the *nDSM* (Figure 8).

By analysing the values for the buildings heights, it was concluded that 28% of the buildings have heights smaller than 2

meters (Figure 9). This situation can be due to: (1) the time difference between the collection of vector data (2012) and the time of the aerial flight (2022) during which some buildings were demolished, or (2) errors related to the process of digitization. So, our approach can also help in updating the national database, in order to identify and remove demolished buildings.

Figure 10 shows a demolished block of flats.

Fig. 8. Building footprints highlighted by the height value

Fig. 9. Statistical distribution of the building heights extracted from the nDSM

Fig. 10. Identifying demolished buildings: a. orthophoto 2012; b. orthophoto 2022

After performing an analysis of these situations, the building feature class was filtered and the updated database was composed of 716 features.

The software used for 3D building models, CityEngine, uses a 3D generation procedure based on a series of CGA rule

files. The principle is based on polygons extrusion, followed by generation of 3D building models. The defined CGA rule (Figure 11) involves setting up some parameters, like the type of roof (gable roof), the inclination angle (18.5°), and the texture used for building facades.

```
@Hidden(Usage, BuildingHeight, UpperfloorHeight)
import Building_Mass_Texturizer: "/ESRI.lib/rules/Facades/Facade_Textures.cga"

@Range(min=2, max=45)
attr height

@StartRule
Lot -->
extrude(height) Mass

Mass -->
Building_Mass_Texturizer.Generate
comp(f) {top: Roof }
report("Volume", geometry.volume)

Roof-->
roofGable(18.5)
```

Fig. 11. CGA rule used to generate 3D building models

Using the updated building footprints and the CGA rule defined previously, the 3D building models were generated (Figure 12).

To evaluate the quality of the performed modelling, 16 randomly distributed points were chosen. The points were located on the rooftops, in one of the corners of the buildings (Figure 13).

Fig. 12. 3D building models

Fig. 13. Points used to evaluate the quality of the 3D building model

The building heights used as ground truth were extracted from a precise LiDAR point cloud. This dataset was collected in 2024 using a RIEGL VQ-1560i airborne LiDAR system, with a point density of 5 points/sq m. This flight provided high-resolution, highly accurate data that served as a reference for model validation. This precise ground truth was crucial for assessing the

altimetric precision of the 3D building models, as it allowed for direct comparison between the height of the building in the models and the actual height of the buildings in the LiDAR point cloud (Figure 14). By using this ground truth, the study ensured the reliability of the results used for urban planning and analysis.

Fig. 14. Example of a building height used in quality assessment

By using the values extracted from the data and displayed in Figure 15, the root mean square error of 1.65 meters was computed.

It should be noted that all roofs were generated with the same angle of inclination (18.5°). Therefore, block-type roofs or those inclined in different

directions can generate significant errors in the calculations. Some errors are due to the way in which the height of the buildings was extracted from the *nDSM*, namely using the building centroids, which in most cases, are situated on the ridge of the roofs, at the highest points.

Fig. 15. Differences in building height for RMSE evaluation

To present the benefits of the 3D building models obtained, we propose a series of applications (Figure 16):

Fig. 16. Applications of the 3D building models

• *Precise Measurements of Buildings in a 3D environment* (Figure 17) - These models allow for detailed measurement of structures, including dimensions, angles, and volumes, which are critical for urban planning, historical preservation, and construction management [26].

Fig. 17. 3D measurements

- *Visibility analysis in different spot points* (Figure 18) – by determining sightlines and obstructions, urban planners can evaluate the visual impact of buildings, optimize placement for surveillance cameras, and ensure compliance with architectural guidelines. Visibility tools can also be used in emergency response planning, ensuring clear sightlines for navigation and evacuation. These analyses contribute to sustainable urban development by balancing aesthetics and functionality.

- *Planning future buildings* (Figure 19) - The integration of 3D data and simulations allows architects and urban planners to design future buildings in harmony with their surroundings. This includes factors such as natural lighting, airflow optimization, and minimizing the visual and ecological impact of new constructions. Research highlights the importance of considering the surrounding landscape to maintain cityscape coherence and reduce urban heat island effects.

Fig. 18. *Visibility analysis*

Fig. 19. *Planning a new building*

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the significant potential of 3D building models in advancing urban planning practices. The integration of high-resolution photogrammetric datasets provides a robust foundation for creating detailed, accurate 3D models of buildings, which are critical for informed decision-making in urban development. The workflow proposed can be applied at national level, by using the building footprints from the national database TopRo5 and the building heights from different datasets based on data availability in different areas. Through the application of advanced computational techniques, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence, urban planners can more effectively analyze and utilize these datasets to simulate various urban scenarios and optimize land use strategies.

Moving forward, it is essential to continue improving algorithms and technologies that can efficiently process large-scale photogrammetric data while reducing error margins. Based on the 3D models and meteorological data, decision-makers can generate different applications. In this sense, by combining a 3D building model with climate and weather data, a digital twin of a city can be developed and maintained in order to be prepared for many possible scenarios. The approach will be applied for the CSA Brasov in the CARMINE project, in order to assess the effects of drought.

While there are obstacles to overcome, the advancements in photogrammetric modelling offer substantial benefits for urban planning. As these techniques continue to evolve, they will likely play an important role in shaping the cities of the

future, ensuring that urban growth is managed in an efficient, sustainable, and responsive manner.

References

1. Biljecki, F., Ledoux, H., Stoter, J., 2016. An improved LOD specification for 3D building models. In: Computers, Environment and Urban Systems, vol. 59, pp. 25-37. DOI: [10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2016.04.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2016.04.005).
2. Biljecki, F., Stoter, J., Ledoux, H. et al., 2015. Applications of 3D city models: State of the art review. In: International Journal of Geo-Information, vol. 4(4), pp. 2842-2889. DOI: [10.3390/ijgi4042842](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi4042842).
3. Bină, I.M., 2021. Contributions to the automation of geospatial data extraction for 3D modelling (in Romanian). PhD thesis, Technical University of Bucharest, Romania.
4. CNC, 2022. Realizarea de true ortofotoplanuri pentru 320 de unități administrativ teritoriale din mediul urban. Available at: <https://cngcft.ro/index.php/ro/domenii/cartografie-si-fotogrammetrie/proiecte-scf/item/216-realizarea-de-true-ortofotoplanuri-pentru-320-de-unitati-administrativ-teritoriale-din-mediul-urban>. Accessed on: March 29, 2024.
5. Fischler, M.A., Bolles, R.C., 1981. Random sample consensus: A paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. In: Communications of the ACM, vol. 24(6), pp. 381-395. DOI:

- [10.1145/358669.358692](https://doi.org/10.1145/358669.358692).
6. Gill, S.E., Handley, J.F., Ennos, A.R. et al., 2007. Adapting cities for climate change: The role of the green infrastructure. In: *Built Environment*, vol. 3(1), pp. 115-133.
 7. Greif, T., Stein, N., Flath, C.M., 2020. Peeking into the void: Digital twins for construction site logistics. In: *Computers in Industry*, vol. 121, ID article 103264. DOI: [10.1016/j.compind.2020.103264](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2020.103264).
 8. Hirschmüller, H., 2005. Accurate and efficient stereo processing by semi-global matching and mutual information. In: *IEEE – Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2005)*, June 20-25, 2005, San Diego, California, U.S.A., vol. 2, pp. 802-809. DOI: [10.1109/CVPR.2005.56](https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2005.56).
 9. <https://www.carmine-project.eu/>, accessed on: November 29, 2024.
 10. <https://www.cartografie.ro/index.php/ro/politica-cookies/item/65-topro5>, accessed on: November 29, 2024.
 11. INSPIRE Knowledge Base, 2024. Available at: https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/overview_en. Accessed on: November 28, 2024.
 12. Jones, D., Snider C., Nassehi, A. et al. 2020. Characterising the digital twin: A systematic literature review. In: *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, vol. 29(part A), pp. 36-52. DOI: [10.1016/j.cirpj.2020.02.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirpj.2020.02.002).
 13. Kappes, H., Katzschner, L., Nowak, C., 2012. Urban summer heat load: Meteorological data as a proxy for metropolitan biodiversity. In: *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, vol. 21(5), pp. 525-528. DOI: [10.1127/0941-2948/2012/0361](https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2012/0361).
 14. Karl, T., Trenberth, K., 2003. Modern global climate change. In: *Science*, vol. 302(5651), pp. 1719-1723. DOI: [10.1126/science.1090228](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1090228).
 15. Lehtola, V.V.P., 2022. Digital twin of a city: Review of technology serving city needs. In: *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 114, ID article 102915. DOI: [10.1016/j.jag.2022.102915](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2022.102915).
 16. Li, Z., Wegner, J.D., Lucchi, A., 2019. Topological map extraction from overhead images. In: *2019 IEEE – International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, October 27 – November 2, 2019, Seoul, South Korea. DOI: [10.1109/ICCV.2019.00180](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2019.00180).
 17. Muja, M., Lowe, D.G., 2014. Scalable nearest neighbor algorithms for high dimensional data. In: *IEEE – Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 36(11), pp. 2227-2240. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.2014.2321376](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2014.2321376).
 18. Pinto, M.C., 2017. Smart cities: Cidades inteligentes em Portugal e o contributo dos SIG para o seu desenvolvimento. Thesis, FLUP - Faculdade de Letras, Universidade do Porto, 295 p.
 19. Prior Costa Parda Filipe, R.I., 2019. Modelling smart cities with CITYGML. Dissertation, Universidade de Lisboa, Technico Lisboa, Portugal, 98 p.
 20. Ratti, C., Baker, N., Steemers, K., 2005. Energy consumption and urban texture. In: *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 37(7), pp. 762-776. DOI: [10.1016/j.enbuild.2004.10.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2004.10.010).
 21. Shragai, Z., Even-Paz, A., Klein, I., 2011. Automatic tie-point extraction using advanced approaches. In: *American Society for*

- Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing Annual Conference, pp. 468-476.
22. Sodiq, A., Baloch, A.A.B., Khan, S.A. et al., 2019. Towards modern sustainable cities: Review of sustainability principles and trends. In: Journal of Cleaner Production, vol. 277, pp. 972-1001. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.106](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.106).
 23. Wang, S., Guo, Z., Liu, Y., 2021. An image matching method based on SIFT feature extraction and FLANN search algorithm improvement. In: Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 2037, ID article 012122. DOI: [10.1088/1742-6596/2037/1/012122](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2037/1/012122).
 24. Wu, B., 2021. Photogrammetry for 3D mapping in urban areas. In: Shi, W., Goodchild, M.F., Batty, M. et al. (eds.), Urban Informatics, Springer, Singapore. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-15-8983-6_23](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-8983-6_23).
 25. Yang, J.Z., 2021. Integrating photogrammetry and GIS for smart city planning. In: Geospatial Science and Technology, vol. 33(2), pp. 112-125.
 26. Zlatanova, S., 2000. 3D GIS for Urban Development. PhD Thesis, ITC, The Netherlands, 222 p. Available at: <http://zlatanova.xyz/PhDthesis/>. Accessed on: November 29, 2024.